

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF INCREASING SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF WOMEN AND GIRLS

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Abstract. *In this article, attention and attitudes towards women are expressed in increasing the social activity of women. Systematic reforms aimed at taking the leading positions of social activity of women in our society and pedagogical aspects of importance at a time when the need for social protection of female students is becoming a state policy are highlighted.*

Keywords: *women, pedagogical aspects, social activity, legal knowledge, higher education, family values.*

INTRODUCTION

In our country, it is determined to increase the social activity of women, to create the necessary conditions for the realization of their abilities and opportunities, and to ensure the unconditional observance of legal and legitimate interests.

In particular, the Decree No. PF-5325 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2018 on "Measures to fundamentally improve activities in the field of supporting women and girls and strengthening the family institution" was announced.

A number of works are being carried out on the basis of this Decree, including the work being carried out in the field of improving the effectiveness of women leaders in the educational process in educational institutions is commendable. In general, in Uzbekistan, important works of national importance are being carried out in order to strengthen the place and status of women in society. After all, the development of society cannot be imagined without women, without their participation. Therefore, a number of measures are being developed and implemented on the scale of our country in order for women to work safely in the family, in state and public affairs, and to realize their rights and interests.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-87 dated March 7, 2022 included in the National program for increasing the activity of women in all aspects of the country's economic, political, and social life in 2022-2026:

- improvement of the normative and legal framework of all-round support for women;
- implementation of comprehensive measures aimed at achieving gender equality, increasing socio-economic and political activity of women;
- creating additional conditions for women's education and involving them widely in the field of science;
- to strengthen women's health, to strengthen measures to protect motherhood and childhood;
- prevention of harassment and violence among women and victims of human trafficking;
- socio-economic support of women detained in penal institutions, who have gone abroad, working in state and public organizations and in the private sector, and to further strengthen the protection of their legal interests;

- further improvement of comprehensive support measures for women in need of social protection;

- honoring enlightened mothers, using their knowledge and rich life experience to strengthen families, raising girls' education and spiritual outlook, as well as creating conditions for their cultural recreation;

- to strengthen the institution of the family, to ensure the stability of a healthy and spiritual environment in families by promoting universal and national values;

- early prevention of crime and violations among women, taking measures to increase legal culture and sense of belonging to large-scale reforms implemented in our country.

Today, it is becoming important to study the changes in the image of the young generation as a result of the views of the head of state on the women's policy and the settlement of social relations in it, as well as the problems of the impact of these changes on social development.

In particular, a number of scientific researches are being carried out in higher education institutions, improving the technology of developing the social activity of female students, developing new pedagogical tools to support their social initiative, developing skills for effective organization of socio-cultural and communicative activities. Moral-aesthetic outlook and socialization of special students are considered as the main factors of development of social activity. Also, as a pedagogue, the mechanisms of social activity, spiritual-cultural, professional, ethical foundations and the development of a conscious attitude to the communicative readiness and ideas of female students, and the development of technocratic thinking play an important role.

The lack of a mechanism for monitoring the execution of admissions, the absence of regulatory legal documents on the social protection of women, and a special research on this scientific topic is necessary.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Philosophical, socio-anthropological issues of development of social activity among female students were studied in the research of A. Begmatov, A. Mavrulov, G. Tulenova, J. Tulenov, M. Kahharova, E. Yusupov and others. B. Adizov, B. Rakhimov, G. J. Tulenovalar, D. Ro'zieva, D. SHArripova, Z. Ismailova, Q. Q. Quranboev, M. Kuronov, M. Makhmudova, N.A. Muslimov, N. Artikov, N. Egamberdieva, O. Jamoldinova, O. Musurmonova, R. Djuraev, O'. Q. Tolipov, U. Mahkamov, K. I. Ibragimov, SH. Mardonov, SH. Sharipov, SH. Shodmonova carried out scientific research.

Foreign scientists such as A. Amutio, A. Smith, A. Yolanda, K. Franco, L. Breeman, R. Sears, R. O. Renye have conducted research on this problem.

As shown in the scientific analysis of Yulchiyeva Dildora Khabibullayevna, we can recall the scientific researches of doctors of Pedagogical Sciences O.Musurmonova and T.Egamberdiyeva on social-cultural, spiritual-pedagogical aspects and "Women's problems". They study such issues as the spiritual world of women, their cultural wealth, their place in the education of the young generation, and their attitude towards them. They do not examine the cultural, spiritual and pedagogical aspects of women's social activity as a problem.

According to Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences R. Mahmudov, "Legal socialization of women is a person, firstly, the formation of her freedom, self-awareness and socialized qualities, and secondly, the qualities of ethnic, spiritual and human qualities that reveal her unique national-humanity. It takes understanding the basics and following them. These two qualities constitute the external legal and social role of a person."

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Due to the strengthening of the role of women in society, their role in society has increased, with a special emphasis on the development and management of the state and society, with a special emphasis on political rights. Today, about 50% of the population, 29% are under 14 years old, 28% are 15-30 years old, 21% are 31-45 years old, 15% are 46-60 years old, and 7% are over 60 years old.

The numbers show that girls between the ages of 15 and 30 are students. Our basic law, our Constitution, recognizes the equal rights of women in all spheres. The interests of women, families, and children have always been a priority in decisions and orders issued by the government.

These efforts are reflected in the active participation of women in society. Increasing attention is being paid to the aspects of increasing the social activity of our women.

Reshaping all modern methods of working with women based on national interests and putting them into practice is an urgent problem. Today, diversity, diversity, and diversity of interests are observed in the women's group itself. On the basis of this diversity, the correct determination of working methods for each young person and their upbringing in the spirit of values is an effective form of protecting women from destructive ideas.

In particular, improving their legal culture and legal literacy, expanding their economic sphere, and improving the social protection system were among the important goals of the state. The reforms implemented in our country have strengthened and strengthened, attention has been paid to the education and upbringing of women. In this regard, from the beginning, in accordance with the President's decision, in the academic year 2020/2021, the recommendation issued by the Ministry of Neighborhood and Family Support, admission rates for the bachelor of additional full-time education were allocated on the basis of a four percent state grant. According to the statement of the State Commission No. 1 of 2020, the territorial distribution of admission rates for women based on an additional four percent state grant is related to the general quotas for admission to higher education institutions of the republic.

According to him, in the new academic year, an additional 940 schools will be allocated to higher education institutions, quotas for full-time undergraduate education. Such reforms serve to further improve their performance. Increasing the status of women in our country, strengthening their socio-political and economic knowledge, and increasing the number of women with higher education.

The main factor for further raising the status of women in our country, ensuring their activity, participation in the reforms implemented in our country - the combination of education and upbringing, can be defined as follows:

First, to give an understanding of socio-political values;

Second, the use of modern methods in pre-school education to make children feel that they are future participants in the country's political life;

Thirdly, to teach subjects aimed at increasing the activity of general secondary education high school students towards social knowledge;

Fourthly, to encourage scientific-theoretical and practical activities in this regard, to study political and legal culture at higher education and subsequent stages, including establishing broad cooperation between educational institutions and state bodies. ;

Fifth, to ensure that objects (cinema, theater, museum, etc.) participate in social and political events, not only in cultural and educational events, but also in forming and improving their spiritual outlook.

Participation in debates in these areas;

Sixthly, ensuring the active participation of women and forming a sense of belonging among young girls to the reforms implemented in our country is the basis of our work in this direction as well in the events of the society.

The role of civil society in ensuring the rights and freedoms of women and raising their social and political level is of great importance. Because non-governmental public organizations, representing the interests of various groups and strata, are recognized as important institutions of modern civil society today. Wide involvement of women in such organizations ensures their direct and indirect participation, as well as their rights and freedoms in state and community management. Today, in our country, women are working in the field of science, education can be divided into two directions. In fact, 72% of employees in this industry are women.

The first direction is to further increase socio-political activity of women working in educational institutions, to further increase their activity, participation in the reforms implemented in our country is one of the important factors of our country's development.

This task can be implemented by further strengthening the activities of primary organizations in educational institutions. In particular, attention is paid to increasing the economic and legal knowledge of women in educational institutions; strengthening the prevention of offenses and crimes, ensuring that teachers comply with the requirements, dress code and etiquette are an important part of the reforms implemented in our country.

The second direction is working with girls studying in educational institutions, including performing the following tasks: increasing the activity of specialists:

b) increase the activity of specialization, educate female students in educational institutions through girls' clubs and spend their free time by attracting them to various clubs;

c) increase students' legal knowledge;

including building their skills on marriage law, marriage contract, marriage and other family relations:

g) preparing young people for life in relevant classes, paying attention to special life skills, profession, family preparation:

d) qualitative organization of psychologists in educational institutions, including personnel, psychological tests.

First of all, one of the most important tasks in the concept of preparing young people for life is the uniform development and implementation. In recommending the following in educational institutions to ensure the screening of persons and women who have applied for marriage to the registry office and to ensure the harmony of measures to strengthen reproductive health and promote the benefits of screening it is permissible to determine the necessity of education, work with young people, organization.

Systematic work is being carried out to prepare them for life: First of all, it is necessary to widely promote the essence of the state policy regarding youth in educational institutions, support the reforms being implemented, and develop the creative potential of young people. Also, in order to increase the spiritual-aesthetic culture, socio-political activity, professional orientation of girls,

as well as wide participation in the activities of the clubs, "Kizlarjon" clubs are being organized in educational institutions.

Reproductive health is one of the effective factors in family and marriage. Initiative, talented active women in this field and winners of the State Award named after "Zulfiya" are involved in propaganda work aimed at strengthening the social and spiritual environment in educational institutions. It is necessary to support and develop the creative potential of talented girls in educational institutions, to promote the intellectual projects created by them. Development of students' interest in learning and reading, formation of communication and speech culture, as well as solving the problems of the educational institution are among the main issues.

Promotion of the creative activity of schoolgirls under the motto "peer-peer" is of practical importance in increasing the socio-political activity of young people. Organization of activities that increase socio-political activity, incorporating spiritual and moral education and national traditions, against the threats of mass culture in various conditions promoted through social networks.

Organization of cultural and educational events, conferences and exhibitions aimed at ensuring systematic participation of women, harmonization of education and training in educational institutions, full manifestation of the talents and abilities of young people. Educational activities among young people, new shows, broadcasts, and organizing columns are also the main factor in the ongoing reforms in our country.

SUMMARY

In short, pedagogical aspects of social development can be developed based on empirical assessment of the activity of female students. Students develop the structural foundations of social activity in relation to professional qualities of girls in personal social experience and position, in the stages of social-pedagogical adaptation, social-political and moral knowledge through the initiation of their social experience.

The practical component of the social activity development model is based on social activity in the criteria determining social activity with the structure of practical-professional activity. It is necessary to effectively use social-pedagogical mechanisms step by step to increase the interest of female students in volunteer groups, to increase the effectiveness of the educational environment.

The role of the educational technology project is to apply the social projects "Ideal student girl", "Student-mother" and develop business games for the development of social activities.

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